

Product experience and luxury values

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Abstract Designing for luxury is a challenge since it requires knowledge on the concept of luxury and how to transfer this knowledge to product design. Literature on the concept of luxury offers a variety of definitions of the term and discusses the role and meaning of luxury by referring to particular disciplines such as economics, sociology and marketing. These studies occasionally touch upon aspects that are associated with luxury products; however there is no specific research that provides guidelines or frameworks to support designers in luxury product development. This study argues that luxury values found across the literature can contribute to defining dimensions of luxury product experience. Presenting the historical background and the definitions of the term 'luxury', this paper explores four different types of luxury values through product examples, and discusses relationships amongst these values. The findings point out a need to study luxury values within different aspects of product design, which can extend the current understanding beyond materialization and into the realms of user-product interaction, design and technology relationships, and design for experience.

Keywords *Luxury, Luxury values, Design for luxury, Product design, User experience*

Introduction

Luxury is a concept that is studied greatly in marketing but not deeply discussed in relation to product design. Existing luxury studies give clues about the communication of luxury through particular consumption phases and offer criteria for how to satisfy consumers of luxury goods. However, they fall short of information about design considerations that can lead to luxury experience through product usage. Similarly, many concepts and brands associated with luxury offer no specific guideline to assess the luxuriousness of their offerings. We need to know more about what it takes to create a luxury experience in products, interactions, and services. Therefore, this paper presents definitions of luxury that have evolved over time, which are then used as a basis to analyse contemporary literature on 'luxury values' together with product examples. The paper provides an understanding of the dimensions of luxury products and points out new research opportunities in the area of 'design for luxury product experience'.

The concept of luxury

Luxury is mostly associated with images of rich and powerful people but it is not easy to reach a universal or concrete definition. It is essentially a relative term (Mehta, 2014). For example, a particular car might be luxury to some people, whilst ordinary to others. In this regard, Kapferer (2012) points out the relativity of luxury by using the definition "the ordinary of the extraordinary".

Etymologically, the word luxury derived from the French term 'luxurie', which means "excess, lasciviousness, and negative self-indulgence". It can be further connected to the Latin word 'luxus', meaning

"soft or extravagant living, sumptuousness, opulence" (Oxford Dictionaries of English, 2015). However, these negative connotations tended to be replaced with positive associations with the Latin root 'lux' (i.e. light), referring to high-value objects made from optically bright and glossy precious materials (e.g. gold) to be used notably by royalty and the church (Brun & Castelli, 2013).

In the Oxford Dictionaries of English (2015) the definitions of luxury are provided as "a state of great comfort or elegance, especially when involving great expense"; "an inessential, desirable item which is expensive or difficult to obtain" and "a pleasure obtained only rarely".

Depending on the context, luxury has been associated with superior qualities of an object or service, high price, high-class, rarity/uniqueness of a particular item, pleasurable experience, as well as unnecessary consumption and extravagant life-styles. Associations with quality tend towards a positive meaning of luxury, whereas associations with opulence tend towards a negative meaning. Throughout history, definitions and the scope of luxury have changed with milestones in sociology, economics and technology. As historical milestones affecting social changes and people's ways of living have been reached, so the concept of luxury has evolved and been redefined. In the ancient world, luxury was seen through buildings symbolizing wealth and power, whilst luxury items were presented as tributes to god(s) (Kapferer, 2012). However, indulgence in individualistic, excessive pleasures was not accepted as a virtue. In early industrial times, trade opportunities led society and individuals to become generally wealthier, making

luxury accessible to a larger and more diverse population. Later in the eighteenth century, society faced major events including liberalisation, democratisation, and women's rights movements, followed by the industrial revolution. In combination, these events brought a considerable rise in the living standards of middle and upper classes and contributed to luxury becoming more affordable to a wider populous (Kapferer & Bastien, 2009). Today, with shared changes in social life such as increased income, delayed marriage, and smaller families, people have more discretionary income to spend on their own luxuries (Silverstein & Fiske, 2003). Accordingly this brings into focus the relativity of the term luxury, since every social class can have their 'own kind' of luxuries.

Emergence of luxury brands

As luxury has strong connections with consumption, the positive and negative connotations of luxury have inevitably evolved with economic developments. The emergence of an industry or 'market segment' for luxury goods and luxury brands draws back to the nineteenth century's industrial revolution and the establishment of companies seeking to produce exceptional products for the taste of the social elite at that time (Antoni et al., 2004). High volume industrial production of luxury goods versus relatively slow local economic growth led to increasing emphasis on export sales to reach customers in other countries, which is reflected in the global operation basis of many of today's luxury companies (Antoni et al., 2004). Through the growth of business in the twentieth century, these companies broadened their customer base and earned a universal reputation for their "superior quality, durability, performance and design" (Brun & Castelli, 2013). Nowadays, the brand identity of such companies is in itself a symbol of luxury. In other words, although the quality of the product or offering is still vital, the concept of luxury has become increasingly bounded within marketing and brand communication.

So what makes certain brands or products 'luxury'? Adam Smith (1776) refers to luxury as "consumption of luxury products" and proposes the classification of consumption as: i) "necessary consumption to maintain life", ii) "basic consumption for normal growth and prosperity of people and communities", iii) "affluent consumption of goods that are not essential for growth and prosperity" and iv) "luxury consumption of goods that are in limited supply, difficult to procure and/or very expensive" (in Berthon et al., 2009).

Other sources in literature do not limit the concept of luxury to rare and very high priced products. For example, Kapferer (1997) suggests the qualities of a luxury brand as: "quality, beauty, sensuality, exclusivity, history, high price, and uniqueness". Whereas, Antoni et al. (2004) offer a list covering: "excellence, brand aura, and desirability". Reinmoller (2002) distinguishes luxury products from standard products by claiming that luxury products exceed the level of 'standard products' by "use of material, processes, packaging, distribution and promotion" to

provide "pleasure and indulgence". Brun and Castelli (2013) also investigated the constitution of luxury products and brands, and provided a more comprehensive list of answers, which they call "the critical success factors of luxury (CSF)" – proposed as a combination of selected definitions of luxury brands and products found in literature. Under CSF, a luxury product or brand should have the following aspects:

i) consistently delivering premium quality; ii) a heritage of craftsmanship; iii) emotional appeal (going beyond the technical specifications of a product); iv) global reputation of the brand; v) an association with a country of origin (e.g. 'Swiss' watches); vi) superior technical performance (e.g. luxury sports cars such as a Porsche Cayman); vii) elements that establish uniqueness/exclusivity (e.g. exclusivity generated by the specific manufacturing method, such as slightly uneven surfaces of mouth-blown glass vases); and, viii) "the creation of a lifestyle (e.g. the 'luxury of spontaneity' concept of Bentley Motors, which suggests particular routes in different continents to be explored by Continental GT customers) (Brun & Castelli, 2013).

Luxury values

In this paper, we explore the particular qualities or concepts (e.g. desirability, exclusivity, indulgence) that luxury brands and products are associated with. The intention is to lay foundations for a structured approach towards designing for luxury product experience, by first exposing the dimensions that define 'luxury' in the context of consumer products. These dimensions are discussed as 'luxury values'. Brands position themselves according to these luxury values, which also become incorporated into their design decision-making processes. Studies within the field of marketing – which has a direct link to product design – are found to focus on up to four main strands of luxury values, namely: 1) **financial value** (Wiedmann et al., 2013), 2) **functionality** (Reddy & Terblanche, 2005) or **functional value** (Berthon et al., 2009; Wiedmann et al., 2013), 3) **symbolic** (Berthon et al., 2009; Reddy & Terblanche, 2005) or **social value** (Wiedmann et al., 2013; Kapferer and Bastien, 2009), and 4) **experiential** (Berthon et al., 2009), **individual** (Wiedmann et al., 2013) or **personal value** (Kapferer & Bastien, 2009). These main strands are brought together in Figure 1.

In the following sections these values are discussed one by one and in relation to each other, with reference to product examples. In doing so, a better understanding of the relationship between product experience and luxury values is intended to be constructed.

Financial value

Financial value is directly related to the monetary worth of a product (Ahtola, 1984). Wiedmann et al. (2009) claim that financial value does not always have to reference the point-of-sale price, it can also refer to an investment value (e.g. an art object predicted to increase in financial value over time).

The retail price of a luxury product can be linked with

Figure 1. Four luxury values relevant to design.

Figure 2. Rolex Pearlmaster 39 (left), Richard Mille RM 027 (right).

several product features including valuable materials or embodied technologies. Oakley (2015) explains that some luxury watches obtain their high retail price from valuable gems, such as the Rolex Pearlmaster, whereas for other watches the high prices stems from high-technology processing of materials including carbon fibre and lithium titanium alloys, used for example in the Richard Mille RM 027 (Figure 2).

Functional value

Purchasers of non-luxury products of course expect that their purchases work properly. In the case of luxury products, the expectation is of 'perfect' functioning and service. This expectation overlaps with the core benefits that Wiedmann et al. (2013) lists: quality, uniqueness, usability, reliability, and

Figure 3. Bentayga SUV on the road (Bentley Motors, 2015).

durability. The core benefits are provided through design details that combine the highest quality materials, technology, engineering, etc. Reddy and Terblanche (2005) conclude that for some brands (e.g. Porsche), the value placed on technical superiority is a key brand attribute – thus the functional value of Porsche cars is a principle determinant of their luxuriousness. Berthon et al. (2009) state that every luxury brand has its material embodiment and the functional value is defined by how the brand's products perform and are experience in use in the material world, rather than what the product 'represents'.

Functional value is crucial to luxury car manufacturers, whose commercial success is based on superior performance and technical expertise. To illustrate, Bentley's 2015 Bentayga SUV (Sport Utility Vehicle) was released as the world's fastest SUV, with a top speed of 301kph (Figure 3). The vehicle is promoted by the company "with innovation at its heart, it displays unprecedented power, speed and efficiency, setting new standards in the SUV sector." (Bentley Motors, 2015).

Symbolic Value

Symbolic value can be defined as the creation of meanings through exposure to luxury brands, products or services. Symbolic value has two aspects: i) meaning created by a brand to symbolize its identity to society, and ii) socially constructed meaning that is assigned to the consumers of a particular brand by society. To exemplify, as Berthon et al. (2009) claim, "...a Ferrari may signal wealth, prestige, and performance, and it can be used to constitute and reinforce the owner's self-image as well."

Luxury brand identity is based on attributes including wealth, prestige, heritage, craftsmanship, superior quality, expertise, country of origin, uniqueness, etc. Different brands may place different emphasis on these attributes, and prefer different strategies in relation to their promotion. For example, Montblanc (predominantly known for its luxury pens and watches) constructs narratives based on its heritage of craftsmanship and explains this as: "creating an invisible bond between craftsmen's souls and their

Figure 4. Frederic Constant watch and fine manufacturing process in Geneva, Switzerland (Frederic Constant, 2015).

customers' soul" (Montblanc, 2015). On the other hand, Rolex chooses a different strategy, and associates its own brand with James Cameron's identity and lifestyle. They promote their superior quality by designing a showcase watch – the Rolex Deepsea Challenge model – to accompany James Cameron in "his journey to deepest place on earth" (2012). As another strategy, brands can emphasize connections and affinity to their country of origin. Kapferer and Bastien (2009) elaborate on this, claiming that a luxury product is a small fragmentation of the culture from which it is produced. Furthermore, a specific geographic location can play an important role in delivering exclusivity in a particular luxury product sector. For example, as with many Swiss watchmakers, Frédérique Constant operates within the watchmaking heritage of Geneva, which became known as a major centre for the creation and production of fine timepieces from the 18th century (Figure 4).

In an alternative approach, Chanel communicates its uniqueness through a set of icons, such as their logo (the intertwined C's), "little black dress", and the number five (Grigorian et al., 2014).

All of these strategies are examples for how symbolic value contributes to luxury brand perception. However, symbolic value can also be formed – as suggested by Reinmoeller (2002) – within social settings, through repeated interaction between people sharing similar interests and knowledge. Kapferer and Bastien (2009) also touch upon this, where membership of a particular group or community is reached through a common usage and ownership of luxury products – in other words, the concept of 'social luxury consumption'. In such instances, people use luxury brands to create a self-image, to present their wealth, prestige, au courant taste etc. to others, and to become conspicuous within social circles (Vigneron & Johnson, 2004).

Luxury brands transfer their symbolic value to society via promotion strategies (e.g. creating narratives, association with celebrities etc.) and make their brand recognizable by setting some exclusive features (e.g. icons, distinguished style and design). People can recognize these brands from their promotion strategies and exclusive features, and associate customers owning and using those branded products as being sympathetic to, and reflective of, the symbolic value communicated by the brand.

Figure 5. Montblanc M pen.

Experiential value

Experiential value is related with an individual person's experience with a luxury product. This experience involves "sensations, feelings, cognitions and behavioural responses" evoked by a specific "design and identity, packaging and communications" (Berthon et al., 2009, p.10).

Kapferer and Bastien (2009) discuss experiential value under their heading 'personal luxury consumption', implying that luxury consumption is for individual satisfaction. According to Wiedmann et al. (2013) individual satisfaction includes not only materialistic aspirations and hedonic motives but also the strengthening of a person's self-identity. Experiential value depends on the subjective taste of customers, and deals with the personal, hedonic value that is found in a brand (Berthon et al., 2009). For example, some Bang & Olufsen customers may choose to buy a loud speaker for the high fidelity sound it offers, whereas others may choose that particular speaker for its distinctive design and manufacturing details. Another example is a Montblanc M pen (Figure 5), offering noticeably different experiences in use, such as the iconic 'sound' of its cap, comfortable writing, and automatic alignment of the cap and the body – each of which will appeal in different measures to different customers.

Experiential value is not only about qualities embodied within a product, but also about the wider presentation and offering of a product. The design and ambience of the shop that a product is presented in, as well as the interaction with salespeople, can contribute to (or detract from) the feeling of luxury as a sense of refinement, contentedness and exclusiveness. Creation of experiential value by luxury product presentation is exemplified by Grigorian et al. (2014) with the Le Labo perfume experience. Le Labo offers a tailor-made experience to its customers by preparing perfumes in front of them. This ritual concludes with perfume bottles personalized with the customer's name (Figure 6).

Discussion

To this point, the paper has reviewed definitions of luxury, evolution of the meaning of luxury through time, the emergence of luxury brands, and the values that contribute to achieving a luxury experience from brands and products. Attention is now given to how those values are interconnected and how relationships between luxury values can be observed.

Figure 6. The Le Labo Perfume Experience.

Relationships between the four luxury values

To create a luxury experience, brands take all four values into account but may position themselves differently by concentrating on each value at a different level (Figure 7). For example a luxury car brand may promote a newly released car with its functional (high performance, durability) and financial (technology) value whereas a perfume company may emphasize more on individual (scent) and symbolic (iconic bottle, logo, scent etc.) value (Figure 7).

Whilst the four values have been explained individually in the paper, it is worth noting the possibility that the values may also influence each other, such as a particular value contributing to the creation of other values or one product property becoming associated with more than one value.

Financial value is regarded as having a significant effect on other values, since all the other values are the result of brand investment through money and time. These investments are reflected in the high retail price of luxury products. A brand can initially aim to create a product with a high financial value or it can prioritize other luxury values that will, over time, build a high financial value. The relationship between financial value and other values is presented as

follows.

- **Financial and functional value:** *Dubois et al. (2001) point out high price as the indicator and result of excellent quality. Functional value derives from a good combination of design, high quality materials, advanced technologies and engineering. All these aspects have an unavoidable financial cost due to time, access to expertise, investment in research and development, etc.*
- **Financial and symbolic value:** *High financial value makes a luxury product accessible only to a minority of people, which in turn converts that luxury product into a symbol of wealth. Vigneron and Johnson (2004) name this process as “conspicuous consumption”, which corresponds to having and using luxury brands as a means of social representation and status.*
- **Financial and experiential value:** *While making investments, luxury companies take into account all production and consumption phases ranging from iconic design development to end product advertisements, from the shopping experience to concierge. These investments enhance the experiential value but also come at a financial cost, which is inevitably passed on through high retail prices.*

Figure 7. Different products or brands show a distribution of emphasis across four luxury values.

If a product fails its function, it cannot offer quality tangible and social interactions. In this regard, symbolic and experiential values are valid or significant only so long as functional value is maintained. The effects of functional value on other luxury values can be summarised as follows.

- **Functional and experiential value:** *Products with high functional value help users to maintain their particular luxury lifestyle. For example, a luxury sports car (e.g. McLaren 570S) can offer such a grand tour travel experience that enables its users to explore long distances with exhilaration and adrenaline rushes thanks to its technical superiorities (quality materials and high performance).*
- **Functional and symbolic value:** *Using a luxury product with high functional value is the indicator of a refined taste that enhances one's self-representation within a social group. However, sometimes it is difficult to find a balance between functionality and symbolic value of a brand. For example, for most of the luxury brands that take their symbolic value from heritage or craftsmanship, it can be a challenge to successfully integrate advanced technologies.*

As all values are at some point intertwined, there is also a link between experiential and symbolic values. They might support or contradict each other depending on the context of luxury consumption.

- **Experiential and symbolic value:** *Symbolic value is related with what a luxury brand or product means to others, whereas experiential value is defined as the meaning to an individual (owner, user). There are some cases where a person's individual experience blends into their social experience as they share the appreciation of luxury product services. For example, luxury cars not only offer the pleasure of driving and the feel of a craftsman's touch through handmade interiors, but also the privilege of becoming a member of a 'select few' with a refined taste and means to indulge it. Nevertheless, experiential value and symbolic value can also manifest in a contrast, as in the example of wearing an uncomfortable shoe (low functional and experiential value) only because of what its brand represents (high symbolic value).*

Conclusions

This paper has provided a theoretical discussion on luxury values in relation to product experience. The review of literature on the concept of luxury revealed the existence of four main luxury values (functional value, financial value, symbolic value, and experiential value), which have tended to be discussed within the sphere of marketing. It is evident that luxury product features, luxury in use and luxury in relation to technology are all areas that have been overlooked in the literature and create opportunities for design research.

Previous studies have focused on how to create a luxury experience through marketing strategies rather than through luxury product features. There are some design concepts clearly associated with luxury (e.g.

quality, craftsmanship, multimodality) but how these concepts are reflected into and through product design is difficult to ascertain from literature. Therefore, this paper investigated the four luxury values in detail and discussed their relationships accompanied by product examples from different sectors. While referring to these examples, focus was given on those product features contributing to luxury experience, alongside promotion strategies that make a product appealing to a luxury market.

Another research opportunity for product design revealed by the paper is the need to understand how luxury is constructed through user-product interaction. Luxury is invariably seen as the combination of quality materials and technology, alongside specific production methods, but how luxury comes to light while users are interacting with products and information, beyond a materialization perspective, is an important design research question.

Finally, the traditional definition of luxury (e.g. heritage of craftsmanship, material combinations) challenges and is challenged by the application of advanced technologies. Especially in consumer electronics where such 'hi-tech' is adopted, it can be hard to maintain delivery of a luxury look and feel, at least in a traditional sense.

By exploring luxury values and product design, this paper has contributed to the identification of dimensions of luxury product experience that may be subsequently assembled within a framework of 'design for luxury'. In other words, the paper has provided an alternative approach to previous studies, which have tended not to be focused on product design considerations and their relationship to luxury values. In combination, the challenges and opportunities identified through the paper set a research agenda for better understanding of how to design for luxury experience with products.

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